

**ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK MODELING FOR MULTI-PARAMETER
PERFORMANCE PREDICTION OF ELECTRONICALLY COMMUTATED FAN COILS
BASED ON EXPERIMENTAL DATA**

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ABSTRACT

The main problems with the selection and operation of fan coils in air conditioning systems impact thermal comfort and energy efficiency, and research on fan coil performance at various operating points is inadequate. No research on artificial neural networks has been undertaken about a concealed ceiling-type electronically commutated motor fan coil that has been subjected to extensive experimental assessments. Four Artificial Neural Networks were trained using 1700 test points to predict the thermal performance and capacity as a main aim. The experiments were conducted in a test apparatus designed according to related standards and an indoor air and heat exchanger fluid regime based on international test norms. The first model estimated air flowrate using six input parameters. The second one estimated air outlet temperature and total cooling capacity using five input parameters. Then, the third one estimated heat exchanger fluid side pressure loss using five input parameters. Lastly, the fourth one estimated air outlet temperature, fan power, and total cooling capacity using eight input parameters. The Levenberg-Marquardt training algorithm was employed in the feedforward backpropagation multilayer perceptron network model comprising 10 neurons in the hidden layer. The deviation obtained for the air flowrate was -0.255% in the first one, while the deviations obtained for the air outlet temperature and cooling capacity were -0.195%, -0.012%, respectively, in the second one. In the third one, the fluid pressure loss exhibited a deviation of -0.014%. In contrast, the air outlet temperature, cooling capacity, and fan power exhibited deviations of +0.045%, -0.014%, and +0.283%, respectively, in the fourth one. This study promotes energy-efficient industries using artificial intelligence-driven performance modelling as a collaboration sample between university and industry.

Keywords: Fan Coil; AMCA 210; Eurovent; Machine Learning; Artificial Neural Network; Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm

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1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the importance of indoor air quality and air conditioning is progressively escalating concerning human health, quality of life, and comfort. Multiple studies have shown that a substantial amount of an individual's time is spent in indoor surroundings [1,2]. While maintaining thermal comfort via interior air conditioning, it is also essential to optimize energy use to reduce environmental effects. The fan coil unit is a prevalent system used for heating, cooling, ventilation, and air conditioning in diverse environments, including businesses, hotels, hospitals, and high-rise structures. These devices operate alone or as components of a centralized air conditioning system to control interior temperatures. A fan coil unit operates by filtering and conditioning air via a heat exchanger, aided by a fan. Due to the growing relevance of interior comfort and technical advances, fan coil unit energy efficiency research is developing. Modern designs prefer electronically commutated (EC) motor fan coils over three-stage alternating-current (AC) ones because of their precise control mechanisms, lower noise, and lower energy consumption. Thus, this article's experiments used EC motor fan coils. European Committee of Air Handling and Refrigeration (EUROVENT) certification assures these fan coils meet testing standards. Before reporting the findings to the certification agency, fan coil performance characteristics are rigorously evaluated under prescribed circumstances. The efficiency and performance of fan coil units are often evaluated by comparing their heating or cooling capabilities to their electrical power consumption. The EUROVENT certification authority uses the fan coil energy efficiency ratio (FCEER) for assessing cooling performance and the fan coil coefficient of performance (FCCOP) for evaluating heating performance [3]. This standardized method facilitates the comparison of various fan coil types via a singular efficiency metric.

Selecting the appropriate fan poses a significant challenge for makers of fan coils and fan coil units: The fan drive must not only provide the requisite output and function silently, but it must also be compatible with installation inside the fan coil housing, and its working principle must align with the specified criteria. This significantly impacts energy consumption and, therefore, operational expenses. AC and EC drives distinguished by their optimal performance, dynamics, and precision of speed. Ventilation systems that save energy and space are essential in contemporary traffic technology due to their high-pressure stability, minimal noise output, and extended durability. They regulate the temperature of passenger compartments and cool technical equipment. Currently, they are used across several industries—specifically in contexts requiring the efficient and intelligent movement of air, as well as in applications where miniature drives function with reliability and precision. In both industrial and private sectors, individuals encounter a multitude of these items daily, sometimes without conscious

awareness. In the medical and laboratory sectors, stringent cleanliness standards must be adhered to. In electronic cooling, optimal air performance and minimal noise are key considerations. In constructing systems, long-term durability and efficiency are crucial, particularly for heating, ventilation, or air conditioning.

Identifying the ideal operating conditions for fan coil units is a considerable problem owing to the intricacies of HVAC systems and the many elements affecting their performance. Executing several trials is essential for acquiring precise performance data; yet, this method is sometimes laborious, resource-demanding, and restricted by the capabilities of testing facilities. Recent improvements in Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and machine learning (ML) methods provide a viable alternative. By using data from a restricted set of tests, ANN models may proficiently discern intricate correlations between input variables and performance indicators, enabling precise predictions of system behavior across diverse settings. These artificial intelligent (AI)-driven methodologies not only diminish the need for significant physical testing but also augment the efficiency of performance assessments, becoming invaluable instruments for improving Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system operations. Recent research has increasingly concentrated on integrating breakthroughs in fan coil technology with developing computational methodologies, including using AI and ML to improve HVAC system efficiency. EUROVENT certification guarantees uniform performance evaluations, but AI-driven prediction models provide a supplementary method by enhancing operational parameters in real-time. Researchers want to refine energy consumption estimates, boost system flexibility, and improve overall interior comfort by incorporating AI-based approaches, including ANN. These breakthroughs enable a new age of intelligent temperature control, as shown by research investigating ANN applications in HVAC optimization. For instance, Lu et al. [4] conducted a case study using machine learning techniques to examine energy consumption and thermal comfort in radiant floor and fan coil cooling systems. The research used a self-constructed experimental apparatus and seven machine learning algorithms, revealing the random forest model's superiority in accurately forecasting operating temperature and energy usage. Similarly, Yang et al. [5] used an ANN model to evaluate air humidity levels in air conditioning systems, pinpointing elements that affect heat and mass transfer during evaporation. Notwithstanding some inconsistencies between the model's predictions and actual results, the ANN model demonstrated encouraging outcomes for enhancing humidity regulation. Abdelghany et al. [6] investigated ANN applications by developing a prediction model for the friction factor and Nusselt number in pulsating flow inside conically coiled tubes. Their results showed a robust association between ANN-predicted and experimental values, substantiating the effectiveness of AI-driven modeling in HVAC applications.

Kim and Cho [7] examined the efficacy of ANNs in improving airflow rates and temperature regulation in variable air volume (VAV) systems. Their research demonstrated that ANN-based control algorithms significantly decreased energy consumption in supply fans and preheater coils, highlighting the

efficiency of AI in dynamic HVAC control systems. Çolak et al. [8] used ANN modeling to ascertain pressure drop, total cost, and total heat transfer coefficients, emphasizing the need of choosing pertinent input parameters to improve model precision. Lee et al. [9] advanced these results by creating a control algorithm for conventional VAV systems that optimally established air handling unit (AHU) set-points, resulting in significant cooling energy savings. Further research by Alamin et al. [10] presented an ANN model aimed at forecasting the power usage of a fan coil system, highlighting the significance of AI in energy-efficient building management systems. Chung et al. [11] concentrated on the optimization of variable refrigerant flow (VRF) systems using ANN, demonstrating the efficacy of AI-driven control systems in diminishing cooling energy use and enhancing indoor temperature regulation. The use of ANNs in thermal system modeling has been thoroughly examined in recent research. Mohanraj et al. [12,13] performed extensive evaluations of ANN applications in refrigeration, ventilation, and heat pump systems, offering insights into AI-based optimization methods for energy-efficient HVAC operations. Xie et al. [14] created an ANN model to establish a relationship between friction factors and Nusselt numbers in heat exchangers, attaining good predictive accuracy with little departure from experimental data. Yigit and Ertunc [15] used ANNs to forecast air outlet temperature and humidity in wire-on-tube heat exchangers, therefore substantiating the viability of AI-driven modeling for HVAC performance evaluation. Moreover, Mohseni et al. [16] showed the efficacy of ANN models in predicting room temperatures by using readily quantifiable data, including indoor and outdoor temperatures, electrical power use, and ventilation flow rates. Their study demonstrated that non-linear ANNs surpass conventional linear estimate techniques in forecasting operating temperature fluctuations. Kalogirou [17] further substantiated the uses of ANNs in energy systems by examining their function in solar energy modeling, building energy assessment, and HVAC system optimization.

The energy consumption of a fan coil unit may be reduced by choosing an optimum model that equilibrates fan power use with heating and cooling demands. The selection process is influenced by many criteria, including initial investment cost, unit size, type of heat exchanger, type of motor, noise levels, and operating efficiency. Performing experimental research to get performance data is crucial for assessing these characteristics and identifying optimum operating settings. Nonetheless, conducting comprehensive experimental investigations presents difficulties owing to time restrictions, constraints of testing facilities, and the accessibility of calibrated measuring devices. The literature review above indicates that no ANN work has been done on the investigated type of fan coil that has undergone so many experimental tests in accordance with international standards.

This research intends to evaluate the performance characteristics of hidden ceiling-type, cabinetless EC motor fan coil units via testing of air flow rate and thermal capacity (cooling capacity). The airflow rate and overall cooling capacity of the fan coil unit were determined using experimental test data, and uncertainty assessments were conducted to evaluate error margins. This extensive, standardized experimental approach addresses the identified literature gap by enabling the development of robust

models based on 1700 test points, an unprecedented scale for this specific concealed ceiling-type EC fan coil, thereby advancing performance modeling beyond limited data applications found in previous studies. Additionally, four unique ANN models were created to quantitatively forecast essential performance metrics using experimental data from 1700 test sites. The ANN outcomes were juxtaposed with experimental data to assess inconsistencies, underscoring the potential of AI-driven prediction models for enhancing HVAC system performance. This research advances energy-efficient HVAC technology by showcasing the efficacy of EC motor fan coils and AI-driven performance modeling. The results underscore the significance of incorporating ANN techniques into HVAC system design, hence facilitating superior energy optimization and greater indoor temperature regulation.

2. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

With the increasing focus on indoor comfort and technological advancements, research on enhancing fan coil unit energy efficiency has gained momentum. Modern designs favor EC motor fan coils over traditional three-stage AC models due to their precise control, lower noise levels, and reduced energy consumption. Consequently, this study employs EC motor fan coils in its experiments. To ensure performance standardization, EUROVENT certification evaluates fan coils under strict test conditions, establishing a classification system upheld by an independent European organization. Certified fan coils must meet specific criteria and undergo rigorous testing before results are submitted for validation. Performance and efficiency are assessed by comparing heating or cooling capacity against power consumption, using the EUROVENT-defined FCEER for cooling and FCCOP for heating. This standardized approach enables a direct comparison of different fan coil models. Experiments of concealed ceiling-type, ductless and cabinetless fan coils of 10 different sizes and capacities were carried out in the Research and Development Air Conditioning department laboratory in Alarko Carrier Gebze factory within the scope of the experimental studies. The experiments were conducted in an experimental setup and experimental room designed in accordance with Air Movement and Control Association (AMCA) and American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) laboratory test method standards. Fan coils were tested with self-controlled EC motors operating within a 0-10 VDC range, using a 0.5 VDC signal frequency within a 2-8 VDC signal range. Experiments were limited to the 2-8 VDC operating range due to the risk of overheating the fan coil motor below 2 VDC and the need to achieve the desired capacities at 8 VDC. The fan coil external static pressure was considered within the 0-60 Pa range in the tests. The schematic illustration and actual image of the fan coil experimental setup designed by Alarko Carrier in accordance with the pertinent standard, is presented in Figure 1. This experimental setup was employed in the experiments and was designed in accordance with the ANSI/AMCA 210-16 standard [18].

The experimental setup basically includes flow regulators to increase the smoothness of the air flow fed by the fan coil, static pressure and temperature measurement points, nozzles to obtain the air volumetric

flow rate of the fan coil, and a radial fan with an EC motor with internal 0-10 VDC control at its outlet. Flow regulators regulate airflow to reduce irregular airflow and turbulence, enabling more accurate and precise measurement of the static pressure of the air supplied to the fan coil. This ensures that the average static pressure of air samples taken from different points in the experimental setup yields more accurate results. In the experiments, multiple pressure loss measurement points are located at the fan inlet and outlet points using pressure gauges to measure the total static operating pressure loss of the fan coil fan. The experimental setup simulates the external static pressure drop required based on the air flow rate of the fan coil under actual operating conditions. The EC motor-driven radial fan connected in series to the end of the experimental setup and the fan coil is used to balance and adjust the pressure drop in the experimental setup. During the experiments, this fan was proportionally controlled to maintain static pressure balance. Air samplers were used to determine the relative humidity of the air inside the thermally insulated test setup. Similarly, air samplers were used immediately in front of the fan coil inlet plenum to determine the humidity of the air entering the fan coil. A total of 9 parallel nozzles, positioned in accordance with the standard between the flow regulators and the radial fan at the outlet of the test setup, were used. The static pressure loss of the nozzles is measured using a high-precision differential pressure transducer to calculate the volumetric flow rate of the fan coil. During the experiments, depending on the air velocities in the nozzles, the relevant nozzles were left open while the other nozzles were closed with a seal to prevent air passage. Which nozzles would be kept closed and which would be kept open to ensure homogeneous air flow was predetermined based on the symmetry of the open nozzles.

The fan coil test setup is located inside the test laboratory, which is isolated from the external environment and has thermal insulation. It is imperative that the properties of the inlet air be cooled by the fan coil remain constant and unaltered throughout the course of the experiments. This encompasses a range of factors, including dry bulb temperature, wet bulb temperature, relative humidity, and ambient pressure. To maintain a constant temperature within the air conditioning system of the AHU located within the test laboratory, the heating coil, electric heater and steam humidifier are controlled in proportion to one another. The conditions under which fan coil experiments are conducted are defined in the EUROVENT standard. In this study, the inlet air was conditioned to the conditions specified in this standard in advance of the experiments. Subsequently, efforts were made to maintain these inlet conditions throughout the course of the experiments. Any data obtained outside the specified experimental conditions were excluded from the final data set. The experimental conditions specified in the EUROVENT standard for fan coil cooling experiments are presented in Table 1. The test conditions outlined in Table 1 are in accordance with the requirements set forth in the standards [19]. During the fan coil experiments, instruments calibrated for measurement were employed. In determining the requisite test measurement instruments for fan coil experiments, consideration was given to the measurement tolerances that are necessary. The measurement tolerances applicable to fan

coil experiments are set out in the ASHRAE 79 standard. The instrumentation employed in the experiments is detailed in Table 2. All measurement instruments used in experimental studies have been calibrated. Table 3 illustrates the operating ranges and sensitivity rates of the measuring instruments employed in experimental studies.

After connecting to the fan coil test setup and adjusting the appropriate nozzle opening, the tests are started. The EC motor signal for the test to be performed on the fan coil is adjusted using the room thermostat. Then, the test is adjusted to the external static pressure loss by adjusting the signal voltage of the auxiliary radial fan in the test setup. After the external static pressure loss of the fan coil is adjusted, the relevant EC motor voltage and external static pressure loss test data, such as nozzle opening area, motor power consumption, motor current, power factor, fan speed, and fan operating pressure, are reported. After the test data is reported, the voltage of the radial fan in the test setup is adjusted again to obtain the next set of external static pressure loss data. Once the desired external static pressure loss is achieved, the test data is reported again. In this way, test data is obtained for the relevant EC motor voltage at 10 Pa intervals within the 0-60 Pa external static pressure loss range. During the experiments, water inlet and outlet temperatures and dry and wet bulb temperatures for air inlet and outlet were also reported for fan coil cooling capacity calculation. While recording the experimental data, data points that deviated from the experimental input conditions were also obtained. When evaluating the thermal capacity (cooling capacity) experimental data, data points that deviated from the experimental input conditions were filtered out. Subsequently, all remaining experimental data points were within the experimental input conditions. The experimental results were obtained by taking the averages of these experimental data points within the experimental input conditions. As a result of the experiments, the air volumetric flow rate of the fan coil was calculated using experimental data according to the air flow rate calculation method described in the AMCA 210 standard. The thermal capacity (cooling capacity) of the fan coil was obtained by calculating the total cooling capacity on the water side. At the end of the studies, uncertainty analyses were performed for air flow rate and thermal capacity tests, and the error rates of the experiments were shown.

3. DATA REDUCTION

Using the data obtained by the experimental studies, the air flow rate of the fan coil was first calculated. While calculating the air flow rate of the fan coil, the air velocities passing through the nozzles in the experimental setup were utilized. Nozzle air velocities were determined by measuring the nozzle differential pressure. Using the nozzle air velocities, the air flow rates through the nozzles were determined. Eqs. (1)-(6) were used to calculate the volumetric air flow rate of the fan coil [18].

$$V = Y \times \sqrt{\frac{2 \times \Delta P}{\rho}} \times C \times A \quad (1)$$

$$Y = 1 - (0.548 + 0.71 \times \beta^4) \times (1 - \alpha) \quad (2)$$

$$\beta = \frac{D_l}{D_k} \quad (3)$$

$$C = 0.9986 - \left(\frac{7.006}{\sqrt{Re}}\right) + \left(\frac{134.6}{Re}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$Re = \frac{D \times v \times \rho}{\mu} \quad (5)$$

$$A = \frac{\pi \times D^2}{4} \quad (6)$$

The value of ρ in Eq. (1) represents the density of air and can be calculated using the equations provided in (7)-(9) [20].

$$\rho = \frac{P_a - 0.378 \times P_v}{287 \times T_a} \quad (7)$$

$$P_v = h_u \times (P_{sat}) \quad (8)$$

$$P_{sat} = \exp\left(\frac{17.438 \times T_a}{239.78 + T_a} + 6.4147\right) \quad (9)$$

Once all parameters have been calculated and substituted into Eq. (1), the fan coil air volumetric flow rate was obtained. The results of the experimental studies enabled the calculation of the air volumetric flow rates of the fan coil units. Subsequently, the total cooling capacity of the fan coil was calculated by utilizing the air flow rates. The total cooling capacity of the fan coil was calculated using the data obtained from the experimental studies, with the total heat transfer on the fluid side calculated using Eqs. (10) and (11).

$$Q_{ct} = V_w \times \rho_w \times c_p \times (T_{wi} - T_{wo}) \quad (10)$$

During the experimental studies, it was assumed that the density and specific heat of water remained constant at 999.87 kg/m³ and 4.194 kJ/kg°C, respectively. In cooling experiments conducted on fan coil units, the electric power consumed by the fan coil motor was deducted from the total cooling capacity.

Concurrently, in fan coil heating experiments, the electric power drawn by the fan coil motor was incorporated into the fan coil heating capacity [21].

$$Q_c = Q_{ct} - P_e \quad (11)$$

Errors may be attributed to several factors during experimental studies. Another issue that is as important as obtaining the results after the experiments is the accuracy of the experimental data. For this purpose, after the experiments are performed, uncertainty (sensitivity) analysis should be performed to determine the systematic or constant errors of these experiments. For this reason, uncertainty analyses were performed to determine error rates as a result of the experiments conducted within the scope of this study. In the uncertainty analysis, a certain number of variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n that affect the error rate are included in the calculation equation. The error (deviation) rates that occur when measuring these variables are w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n . W_R can be calculated using Eq. (12), where R is the experimental data that needs to be calculated and W_R is the total error rate that occurs when calculating this experimental data [22].

$$W_R = \pm \left[\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial x_1} w_1 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial x_2} w_2 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial x_3} w_3 \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial x_n} w_n \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

Error rates at 3 different fan speeds were calculated and shown in Table 4 for the air flow rate experiments of a fan coil unit. In addition, for the cooling capacity experiments, error rates at 3 different fan speeds were calculated and shown in Table 5.

4. NUMERICAL MODEL

Four different ANN models were created to estimate and determine the important performance parameters of the experimentally studied fan coil units. The experimental data and the experimental parameters influencing them were evaluated and the input parameters for the experimental data to be estimated were determined. Each ANN model was evaluated within itself and the relationship between the output parameters and the input parameters was determined. In the study, ANN models were created using the feedforward backpropagation multilayer perceptron (MLP) network model. The MLP network model, which is widely used in neural networks, basically consists of three main layers. These layers, which have different numbers of neurons, are the input layer where the training data is introduced, the hidden layer where the numerical parameters are located, and the output layer where the values to be estimated are located. The neurons in each layer are first connected to the neurons in the previous layer. Then, after certain operations, they are connected to the neurons of the next layer [23]. Among ANN network models, MLP network models are widely used due to their high learning abilities and robust structures [24, 25]. An example structure of the MLP network model is shown in Figure 2.

One of the important factors in the design of ANN models is to determine the appropriate training algorithm to train the input parameters accurately and with high estimation ability. In the ANN models designed within the scope of this study, the Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) training algorithm was used as the training algorithm. The LM algorithm, which is frequently used in the development of ANN models, has a high training ability [26, 27]. To achieve low deviation rates in the prediction of experimental data, it is essential to ensure the appropriate grouping of the data during the design of ANN network models. Furthermore, utilization of a sufficient quantity of experimental data is crucial to attain low deviation rates in ANN models. In ANN models where a limited number of experimental data points are employed, the predictive capacity may be diminished, and the deviation rates may be elevated. On the other hand, it is seen that unnecessary use of input parameters in experimental data for the high prediction ability of ANN models does not reduce deviation rates, but rather negatively affects the learning algorithm and increases the deviation rates of ANN models [8]. The features of four different ANN models developed within the context of this study are outlined below.

4.1. ANN Model 1

The ANN Model 1 was developed to estimate the experimentally obtained air flow rates of fan coil units. In the ANN Model 1, the important parameters affecting the fan coil air flow rate were evaluated and determined. Subsequently, these variables were incorporated into the input layer of the MLP network model. The air side static pressure loss of the fan coil and the operating point of the fan coil fan have an impact on the air flow rate. An increase in air side static pressure loss will result in a reduction in the air flow rate provided by the fan coil fan. Conversely, an increase in the operating frequency of the fan coil fan will result in a corresponding increase in the air flow rate provided by the fan. Considering the aforementioned factors, it can be concluded that the dimensions and important notation parameters of the fan coil coils, the operating characteristics of the fan coil fan and the external static pressure are crucial elements influencing the fan coil air flow rate. Based on these criteria, six different input parameters, such as pipe and row number, fin length, circuit number, EC motor voltage and external static pressure loss, were determined as inputs to predict the air flow rate in the ANN Model 1 as shown in Table 6. The network structure of ANN Model 1, comprising 10 neurons in the hidden layer and utilizing the LM training algorithm, is shown in Figure 3a.

4.2. ANN Model 2

The ANN Model 2 was developed to estimate the experimentally obtained air outlet temperatures and total cooling capacities of fan coil units. The air flow rate of the fan coil, the dimensions of the coil, and the other important parameters that are given in Table 7 are significant factors affecting the air outlet temperature and total cooling capacity. Once these factors had been evaluated and determined, they were introduced into the input layer of the MLP network model for ANN Model 2. Considering all the factors, five different input parameters, such as air flow rate, pipe and row number, fin length and circuit

number of coils, were determined as inputs to predict the air outlet temperatures and total cooling capacities in the ANN Model 2. The network structure of ANN Model 2, comprising 10 neurons in the hidden layer and trained using the LM algorithm, is shown in Figure 3b.

4.3. ANN Model 3

The ANN Model 3 was developed to estimate the experimentally obtained water pressure drops of the fan coil. The parameters that exert a significant influence on the water pressure drop of the coil were identified. These were incorporated into the input layer of the MLP network model. The dimensions of the coil and the important notation parameters are the important factors affecting the pressure drop of the water flowing through the coil pipes. Considering these factors, five different input parameters, such as pipe and row number, water flow rate, fin length and circuit number of coils, were determined as inputs to predict the water pressure drop in the ANN Model 3, as demonstrated in Table 8. The network structure of ANN Model 3, comprising 10 neurons in the hidden layer and trained using the LM algorithm, is shown in Figure 3c.

4.4. ANN Model 4

In addition to the initial three ANN models, all input and output parameters were collated in a single ANN model, resulting in the development of ANN Model 4. The objective of ANN Model 4 was also to estimate the fan coil fan power. Eight different input parameters, including pipe and row number, fin length, circuit number of coils, EC motor voltage, external static pressure loss, air and water flow rate, were identified as inputs to predict the air outlet temperature, fan power and total cooling capacity in the ANN Model 4 as provided in Table 9. The network structure of ANN Model 4, comprising 10 neurons in the hidden layer and utilizing the LM training algorithm, is shown in Figure 3d.

4.5. Validation of Developed ANN Model

Within the scope of the study, the Tan-Sig transfer function was employed as the transfer function for the hidden layer of the MLP network model. The Tan-Sig transfer function employed is given in Eq. (13) [28]. The Purelin transfer function was preferred as the transfer function for the output layer of the MLP network model. The Purelin transfer function used is given in Eq. (14) [28].

$$f(x) = \frac{2}{1 + \exp(-2x)} - 1 \quad (13)$$

$$purelin(x) = x \quad (14)$$

There are different performance parameters to evaluate the ability and performance of the designed ANN models to predict experimental data. In this study, the coefficient of determination (R) and mean square error (MSE) parameters, which are frequently used in literature, were calculated and determined

[28]. R and MSE parameters are given in Eqs. (15) and (16), respectively. According to these parameters, the prediction abilities and performances of the developed ANN models were interpreted.

$$R = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{\text{exp}(i)} - X_{\text{ANN}(i)})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{\text{exp}(i)})^2}} \quad (15)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \times \sum_{i=1}^N (X_{\text{exp}(i)} - X_{\text{ANN}(i)})^2 \quad (16)$$

In addition to these performance parameters, the average deviation rates of ANN model results were also determined. At the end of the study, the experimental data and the data predicted by the ANN models were compared and the deviation rates of the predictions were calculated by Eq. (17) [28].

$$\text{Deviation rate} = \left[\frac{X_{\text{exp}} - X_{\text{ANN}}}{X_{\text{exp}}} \right] \times 100(\%) \quad (17)$$

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fan coil units are a commonplace feature of the HVAC sector, employed for the purpose of heating and cooling indoor environments. It is crucial to select fan coil units and ascertain their performance parameters under actual operation. In addition, the effect of these performance parameters on each other should also be examined. For these reasons, it is important to develop models employing diverse methodologies to estimate the performance parameters of fan coil units and to perform numerical studies. The review of the literature in the HVAC sector reveals that ANN models have been effective in predicting the performance output parameters of heating and cooling systems, with low error rates. Accordingly, in the present study, the significant performance output parameters of the fan coil are classified into different categories based on the input parameters, and ANN models are conducted and evaluated. Thus, it is involved in training four distinct ANNs on a subset of the experimental dataset, consisting of 1700 test points, to numerically predict the thermal performance and capacity of a concealed ceiling-type fan coil. The experiments were conducted using a testing apparatus compliant with the AMCA 210 standard and operated under indoor air and heat exchanger fluid conditions as per EUROVENT testing regulations. In the initial ANN, the airflow rate was estimated to be using six distinct input parameters. In the second ANN, the air outlet temperature and total cooling capacity were predicted utilizing five distinct input parameters. In the third ANN, the pressure loss on the fluid side of the heat exchanger was assessed based on five distinct input parameters. In the fourth ANN, the air outlet temperature, fan power, and total cooling capacity were predicted based on eight distinct input

parameters. The LM training algorithm was utilized in network models featuring 10 neurons in the hidden layer. The outcomes of the data set, comprising 1700 derived from experimental investigations, were compared with the projections of ANN models, and the deviation rates of ANN models regarding the performance output parameters were determined. The accuracy and reliability of the ANN models were analyzed in detail with the MSE and R parameters.

The study employs distinct sets of input parameters for each model to guarantee a thorough assessment of airflow rate, cooling capacity, air outlet temperature, and pressure loss. A comprehensive comparison between experimental results and ANN predictions is provided to evaluate the reliability of these models. This section examines the performance of ANN Model 1, concentrating on estimating the air flow rate, which is one of the important parameters of the fan coil. In order to facilitate a more comprehensive evaluation of the numerical modeling results, the outcomes of the experiments and the ANN model are presented in comparison form. The objective data obtained from the experiments and the predicted values are presented in Figure 4 to facilitate an examination of the accuracy of the model developed to predict the air flow rate. Upon examination of the graph in Figure 4a, it becomes evident that the positions of the circles representing the intended experimental air flow data and the blue crosses representing the ANN model results exhibit a notable degree of overlap. To examine the accuracy and reliability of the ANN model results in greater detail, the intended experimental results are presented on the x-axis, and the results predicted by the ANN model are presented on the y-axis in the graph provided in Figure 4b. In this graph, the diagonal line through the center can be defined as the zero-error line, where the experimental results and the predicted results exactly match. From the graph in Figure 4b, it can be seen that the data lies on and around the aforementioned zero error curve. Finally, the results of ANN Model 1 are plotted as shown in Figure 4c to evaluate the margin of deviation (MoD) between the experimental data and the ANN model results against the data points. For this purpose, the differences between the data obtained as a result of the experimental studies and the ANN model results were obtained at each data point. When evaluating the deviation rates in Figure 4c, the deviation rates are low for many of the test data points. In the ANN Model 1 developed to predict the air flow rates of the fan coils, the mean deviation rate was obtained to be -0.255%. To evaluate the developed ANN model, R-value and MSE values obtained as performance parameters were calculated as 0.96848 and 2.24×10^{-2} , respectively. These data obtained by numerical modeling and the graphical figures show that the developed ANN model can predict the air flow rate with acceptable reliability and accuracy.

The study expands on the thorough assessment of ANN models, each tailored to forecast distinct performance parameters, and further examines the precision of each model. Following the evaluation of the predictive efficacy of ANN model 1, which concentrated on airflow rate estimation, focus has now shifted to ANN model 2. This model seeks to estimate the air outlet temperature and total cooling capacity, which are essential thermal performance indicators of the fan coil. In ANN model 2, the air outlet temperature and total cooling capacity, which are important thermal performance parameters of

the fan coil, were estimated. To assess the accuracy of the model devised to predict the air outlet temperature and the total cooling capacity of the fan coil, which are identified as outputs for ANN model 2, the target data obtained from the experiments and the predicted values are presented in Figures 5 and 6. In Figure 5a, it is seen that even though there are points where the prediction values for the air outlet temperature deviate from the experimental data, most of the data points overlap with the circles representing the experimental data and the crosses representing the ANN model prediction results. In Figure 6a demonstrates that the circles representing the experimental data and the pluses representing the ANN model results overlap with great accuracy. To examine the ANN model results in a more understandable and detailed way, the intended experimental results on the x-axis and the results predicted by the ANN model on the y-axis are given in Figure 5b and Figure 6b. Figure 5b shows that most of the data for the air outlet temperature is on and around the zero-error curve. Figure 6b shows that almost all the data for the total cooling capacity output parameter is on the zero-error curve. The deviation rates of the developed model were examined by finding the differences between the ANN model 2 results and the results obtained with experimental data. Figure 5c and Figure 6c show the deviation rates of ANN Model 2 for air outlet temperature and total cooling capacity, respectively. Upon evaluation of Figure 5c and 6c, it was observed that the deviation rates of the air outlet temperature and total cooling capacities were relatively low across most experimental data points. Upon evaluation of the ANN model 2 prediction deviation rates for all experimental data points, it was determined that the average deviation rate was -0.195% for air outlet temperature and -0.012% for total cooling capacity. The MSE and R values expressing the predictive ability of the ANN model were obtained as 6.92×10^{-2} and 0.97312, respectively. The calculated mean deviation values, performance parameters and the obtained graphs show that the ANN model can predict the air outlet temperature and total cooling capacity with acceptable reliability and accuracy.

After assessing ANN model 2, which concentrated on forecasting air outlet temperature and total cooling capacity, the study transitions to another vital performance metric of fan coil units—the water side pressure drop. Precise estimation of pressure loss is crucial for optimizing the hydraulic efficiency of the heat exchanger and ensuring effective system operation. In this context, ANN model 3 was created to forecast water pressure loss based on specified input parameters. This section provides a comprehensive comparison of experimental results and ANN predictions, employing graphical representations in Figure 7 to evaluate the model's accuracy and reliability using the ANN model 3 to predict the water side pressure drop of the fan coil. Figure 7a demonstrates that the circles representing the experimental results and the pluses representing the prediction results exhibit a high degree of overlap. To compare the results on the zero-error curve, Figure 7b depicts the targeted experimental results on the x-axis and the prediction results of the ANN model on the y-axis. Figure 7b demonstrates that the data points are situated along the zero-error line with a high degree of accuracy and minimal error rates. Figure 7c is given to evaluate the deviation rates of ANN model 3 in accordance with the

data points. Figure 7c shows that the deviation rates are close to zero for most of the data points. As a result of the modeling, it was determined that the average deviation rate for predicting the water pressure loss for ANN model 3 was -0.014%. MSE and R values for ANN Model 3 were calculated and obtained as 2.63×10^{-3} and 0.98462, respectively. This average deviation rate and the calculated performance parameters of the ANN model show that the ANN model can be used to predict the water pressure loss.

This study expands on the assessment of prior ANN models by examining the predictive performance of ANN model 4, which aims to estimate several critical output parameters, such as air outlet temperature, total cooling capacity, and fan power consumption. Due to the complex structure of this model, thorough evaluation is essential to confirm its precision and dependability. This section provides a comprehensive comparison of experimental and predicted results, employing graphical representations in Figures 8a, 9a, and 10a to demonstrate the correlation between actual measurements and ANN-based estimations. Figures 8a, 9a, and 10a demonstrate that the circles representing the experimental results and the pluses representing the prediction results exhibit a high degree of accuracy about the variables of air outlet temperature, total cooling capacity and fan power consumption. The positions of the experimental results and the predicted results on the zero-error line are given in Figures 8b, 9b, and 10b for air outlet temperature, total cooling capacity and electricity consumption respectively. Figure 8b shows that many data points for the air outlet temperature are situated within the vicinity of the zero-error line. Figures 9b and 10b demonstrate the accuracy of the prediction values for total cooling capacity and fan power consumption, respectively. To evaluate the average deviation rates of the numerical model, Figure 8c, 9c, and 10c show the deviation rates by data points for air outlet temperature, total cooling capacity and fan power consumption, respectively. The mean deviation rates were determined by finding the differences between the experimental data and the predicted data. The average deviation ratios were obtained as +0.045%, -0.014% and +0.283% for air outlet temperature, total cooling capacity and fan power, respectively. In addition, the performance parameters MSE and R values for ANN Model 4 were calculated as 5.49×10^{-2} and 0.97048, respectively. The mean deviation value, the calculated performance parameters and the presented graphs show that the ANN model can predict the output parameters with reliable accuracy.

The SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) analysis for the air flow rate prediction in ANN Model 1 (Figure 11a) systematically quantifies the contribution of the six input parameters to the model's output, confirming the predictive hierarchy rooted in electro-aerodynamic principles. The analysis is expected to reveal that the EC motor voltage and the external static pressure loss are the most influential features, aligning with the operational dynamics where the fan drive energy (controlled by voltage) dictates the potential flow output, while the external static pressure loss determines the system resistance that diminishes the actual air volumetric flow rate. Specifically, the SHAP values demonstrate that higher EC motor voltage results in a strong positive contribution to the predicted air flow rate, whereas increased external static pressure loss imposes a negative influence on the prediction. The physical coil

geometry parameters (pipe and row number, fin length, and circuit number) provide the static structural context for the air flow, acting as secondary but essential features in defining the fan coil's characteristic curve.

The SHAP analysis for the air outlet temperature prediction in ANN Model 2 (Figure 11b) focuses on identifying the critical thermal and fluidic parameters among the five inputs that govern the fan coil's discharge condition. The analysis confirms that the air flow rate is the primary dynamic predictor of air outlet temperature T_{a2} , given that a higher volumetric flow reduces the air's residence time over the heat exchanger, thereby resulting in higher predicted air outlet temperatures. The coil's structural properties, defined by pipe number, row number, fin length, and circuit number, collectively account for the available heat transfer area and hydraulic distribution, exerting a foundational influence on the thermal effectiveness of the unit. The SHAP values illustrate how the combined influence of these fixed geometrical parameters and the dynamically varying air flow rate precisely modulate the final predicted T_{a2} . The SHAP analysis for the total cooling capacity prediction in ANN Model 2 (Figure 11c) confirms the dominant influence of the air flow rate on the unit's overall thermal performance. Since the Q_c is fundamentally defined by the mass flow rate and the temperature differential, the volumetric air flow rate dictates the quantity of air being conditioned, rendering it the most significant feature in the predictive model. Higher air flow rates are associated with large positive SHAP values, directly increasing the predicted cooling capacity. The geometrical parameters of the coil (pipe/row number, fin length, circuit number) are crucial for establishing the potential for heat transfer by defining the heat exchanger size and efficiency, but the dynamic air flow rate is the key operational variable quantified by SHAP as the main driver for changes in Q_c .

The SHAP analysis for the coil water pressure drop prediction in ANN Model 3 (Figure 11d) isolates the features governing the hydraulic resistance within the heat exchanger. The analysis is dominated by the water flow rate, which is the dynamic variable directly correlating to the fluid velocity and, consequently, the frictional losses within the piping system. The SHAP results demonstrate a pronounced positive correlation between higher water flow rates and increased predicted water pressure drop, reflecting the non-linear relationship between flow velocity and hydraulic resistance. The structural coil parameters (pipe number, row number, fin length, and circuit number) define the internal geometry and flow characteristics, serving as critical context features; notably, the circuit number significantly influences the pressure drop by determining the effective path length and the number of parallel flow circuits.

The SHAP analysis for air outlet temperature prediction within the comprehensive eight-input ANN Model 4 (Figure 11e) highlights the complex interplay between aerodynamic and hydraulic controls in defining the thermal output. In this unified model, both air flow rate and water flow rate are identified as the most consequential features, as they govern the mass transport and thermal exchange on both sides of the coil, dictating the achieved T_{a2} . The inclusion of EC motor voltage and external static pressure loss reveals their indirect, yet substantial, effect on T_{a2} , primarily by modifying the air flow

rate characteristic. This analysis effectively confirms that optimal thermal performance predictions require accurate modeling of both fluid flow dynamics across the heat exchanger, as captured by the most significant SHAP values. The SHAP analysis for total cooling capacity prediction in ANN Model 4 (Figure 11f) confirms the predictive dominance of operational inputs in achieving maximum thermal output, even when considering all eight inputs. Consistent with physical principles, the air flow rate and water flow rate are the primary features positively contributing to the predicted total cooling capacity Q_c . The analysis also reveals the strong upstream influence of the EC motor voltage, acting as the main driver for air movement and capacity modulation, making it a critical control parameter whose input level directly correlates with higher predicted Q_c . The SHAP results thus provide empirical justification for the system control philosophy, demonstrating that maximum capacity prediction relies heavily on maximizing the throughput of both air and water while managing fan power.

The SHAP analysis for the fan power consumption prediction in ANN Model 4 (Figure 11g) provides critical insight into the system's energy utilization by identifying the most significant drivers of electrical consumption. The results unequivocally establish EC motor voltage and external static pressure loss as the predominant features, which align perfectly with the fundamental laws of fan dynamics, where power consumption is directly proportional to operating speed (driven by voltage) and the required pressure head. High EC motor voltage is the primary positive contributor to the predicted P_e , while greater external static pressure loss increases the mechanical work required from the fan, also shifting the prediction positively. The air flow rate maintains a strong, correlated importance, as it is the direct outcome of the power input and system resistance, thus demonstrating the comprehensive and physically consistent feature attribution provided by the SHAP methodology for fan power prediction.

6. CONCLUSION

Important performance parameters such as air volume flow rates, thermal capacities (cooling capacities), and power consumption of concealed ceiling type EC motor fan coil units have been obtained by experimental studies under certain conditions. The performed literature study in the current work demonstrates that no ANN research has been conducted on the specific type of fan coil that has undergone numerous experimental evaluations in compliance with international requirements. Four ANN models were developed to predict key performance characteristics of fan coil units evaluated by experimental investigations according to international standards in a private manufacturing firm. The feed-forward backpropagation MLP network model, which predicts well, was chosen for the suggested ANN models. The MLP network model uses the strong-structured, high-learning LM training method. Tan-Sig and Purelin transfer functions were employed in the MLP network model's input and output layers. Four ANN models' commonly favored R and MSE values were generated to assess their performance and capacity to forecast specified data. The disparities between targeted and anticipated data were used to calculate the average deviation rates of the ANN models. Future research on the ANN subject with other ML methods can extend tested fan models' operating ranges for the purpose of

prediction and enrich the comparison outputs. Moreover, validated ANN methods using experimental databases can be applied to other parts of HVAC systems. As a result, ANN-based HVAC system analysis methods may replace experimental methods for performance assessment. This industry-academic collaboration had tried to use AI-driven performance modelling to improve energy-efficient HVAC systems. The main findings of this research are:

- a. Upon examination of ANN Model 1 that estimates the volumetric flow rate of air in the fan coil, the results showed the average deviation rate was ascertained to be -0.255%. The R and MSE values for ANN Model 1 were calculated as 0.96848 and 2.24×10^{-2} , respectively.
- b. Analysis of ANN Model 2 revealed average deviation rates of -0.195% for air outlet temperature and -0.012% for total cooling capacity. The R and MSE values for ANN Model 2 were calculated as 0.97312 and 6.92×10^{-2} , correspondingly.
- c. An average deviation rate of -0.014% was found in the analysis of ANN Model 3, which predicts the water pressure loss of the fan coil heat exchanger. The R and MSE values for ANN Model 3 were determined to be 0.98462 and 2.63×10^{-3} , respectively.
- d. The average deviation rate of air outlet temperature, total cooling capacity, and fan power was found to be +0.045% for ANN Model 4, -0.014% for total cooling capacity, and +0.283% for fan power. The R and MSE values for ANN Model 4 were calculated as 0.97048 and 5.49×10^{-2} , separately.
- e. Each ANN model accurately predicted air volumetric flow rates, air outlet temperatures, cooling capacities, water pressure losses, and fan power with negligible deviation from the experimental data. Among the models, ANN Model 3 demonstrated the greatest accuracy, whereas all models exhibited dependable predictive performance.

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NOMENCLATURE

- | | |
|-------|-------------------------------|
| A | Nozzle area, m^2 |
| C | Nozzle discharge coefficient |
| c_p | Specific heat of water, J/kgK |

D	Nozzle diameter, m
D_l	Nozzle outlet hydraulic diameter, m
D_k	Channel hydraulic diameter, m
h_u	Relative humidity value of air, %
m	Air mass flow, m ³ /h
P_a	Atmospheric pressure, Pa
P_e	Fan power consumption, W
$P_{e,pred}$	Estimated fan power consumption, W
$P_{e,targ}$	Target fan power consumption, W
P_{sat}	Saturation pressure of air, Pa
P_v	Partial vapor pressure, Pa
P_w	Coil water pressure loss, Pa
$P_{w,targ}$	Target coil water pressure loss, Pa
$P_{w,pred}$	Estimated coil water pressure loss, Pa
$Q_{c,pred}$	Estimated total effective cooling capacity, W
Q_c	Total effective cooling capacity, W
Q_{ct}	Total cooling capacity, W
R	Coefficient of determination
Re	Reynolds number
T_a	Air dry bulb temperature, °C
T_{a2}	Air outlet temperature, °C
$T_{a2,pred}$	Estimated air outlet temperature, °C
$T_{a2,targ}$	Target air outlet temperature, °C

T_{wi}	Coil water inlet temperature, °C
T_{wo}	Coil water outlet temperature, °C
$Q_{c,targ}$	Targeted total effective cooling capacity, W
V	Air volumetric flow, m ³ /h
V_w	Chilled water volumetric flow, l/s
v	Air velocity, m/s
V_{pred}	Estimated air volumetric flow, m ³ /h
V_{targ}	Target air volumetric flow, m ³ /h
Y	Nozzle Expansion Factor
W_R	Uncertainty analysis total error rate, %
ρ	Air density, kg/m ³
ϑ	Specific volume of air, m ³ /kg
ΔP	Nozzle differential pressure, Pa
α	Nozzle inlet and outlet absolute pressure ratio
β	Ratio of nozzle outlet hydraulic diameter to channel hydraulic diameter
μ	Air Dynamic Viscosity, kg/m-s
ρ_w	Water density, kg/m ³

Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
AHU	Air Handling Unit
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMCA	Air Movement and Control Association
ANN	Artificial Neural Network

ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air Conditioning Engineers
DAT	Discharge Air Temperature
EC	Electronically Commutated
EUROVENT	European Committee of Air Handling and Refrigeration
FCEER	Fan Coil Energy Efficiency Ratio
FCCOP	Fan Coil Coefficient of Performance
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
LM	Levenberg-Marquardt
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MoD	Margin of Deviation
MSE	Mean Square Error
R	Coefficient of Determination
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
VAV	Variable Air Volume
VRF	Variable Refrigerant Flow
WC	Water Column

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Table 1. Cooling test conditions of fan coil [19]

Water	Inlet temperature	7 °C
	Outlet temperature	12 °C
Air	Dry bulb temperature	27 °C
	Wet bulb temperature	19 °C

Table 2. Measurement instruments used in experiments

Measuring Instruments	Model
Temperature	RTD/PT100- 3 cables
Relative humidity	Digimax DM-HT-D5V
Power	Digital power meter
Barometric pressure	DM-PT-100-A-1
Nozzle differential pressure	Ashcroft IXLdp
Air static pressure	Ashcroft IXLdp
Water flow meter	Siemens MAG1100
Voltage transformer	Varsan regulated transformer
Revolution (Rpm)	Digimax DMZN96
Water pressure difference	Digimax DM-DPT-300W

Table 3. Sensitivity ratios of the measuring instruments used in the experiments

Measurement instruments	Precision	Operating ranges
Temperature	± 0.05	$-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} - 270\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
Relative humidity	$\pm 2\% \text{ RH}$	$\text{RH } \% 0 - 99.9$
	$\pm 0.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} - 80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
Power	± 0.1	$30\text{ W} - 3000\text{ W}$
Nozzle differential pressure	$\pm 0.25\%$	$\pm 5'' \text{ WC}$
Air static pressure	$\pm 0.25\%$	$\pm 5'' \text{ WC}$
Water flow meter	$\pm 0.2\%$	$0 - 10\text{ m/s}$
	$\pm 1\text{ mm/s}$	$-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} - 50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
Water pressure difference	± 0.1	$0 \sim 20\text{ kPa} \dots 35\text{ kPa} \dots \sim 2\text{ MPa}$ $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} - 80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Table 4. Uncertainty analysis results of fan coil air flow experiments

EC motor voltage [V]	Test results [m³/h]	Error analysis result [m³/h]	Error percentage [%]
8	2176.45	37.78	1.736
6	1741.48	30.15	1.731
4	1287.42	22.32	1.734

Table 5. Uncertainty analysis results of fan coil thermal capacity experiments

EC Motor Voltage [V]	Cooling capacity test result [W]	Error analysis result [W]	Error percentage [%]
4	6642.85	91.92	1.384
6	7997.34	115.64	1.446
8	9702.82	136.4	1.406

Table 6. Input and output parameters of ANN model 1

Input	Output
Pipe number	
Row number	
Fin length [m]	
Circuit number	Air flow rate [m ³ /h]
EC motor voltage [volt]	
External static pressure loss [Pa]	

Table 7. Input and output parameters of ANN model 2

Input	Output
Air flow rate [m ³ /h]	
Pipe number	
Row number	Air outlet temperature [°C]
Fin length [m]	Cooling capacity [kW]
Circuit number	

Table 8. Input and output parameters of ANN model 3

Input	Output
Water flow rate [l/h]	
Pipe number	
Row number	Water pressure drop [kPa]
Fin length [m]	
Circuit number	

Table 9. Input and output parameters of ANN model 4

Input	Output
Water flow rate [l/s]	
Air flow rate [m ³ /h]	
Pipe number	
Row number	Air outlet temperature [°C]
Fin length [m]	Cooling capacity [kW]
Circuit number	Fan power [W]
External static pressure loss [Pa]	
EC motor voltage [volt]	

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 1. a) Schematic representation of the fan coil test setup 1) fan coil, 2) insulated test setup, 3) reduction connection, 4) flow regulators, 5) nozzle, 6) and 7) nozzle differential pressure measurement, 8) auxiliary EC fan, 9) atmospheric pressure measurement point, 10) ambient air temperature and humidity measurement point, 11) fan coil inlet air temperature measurement point, 12) fan coil inlet air humidity measurement point, 13) fan coil external static pressure loss measurement point. b) Actual image of the fan coil test setup. c) Actual image of the fan coil test laboratory 1) fan coil test laboratory, 2) air handling unit, 3) air channels

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the MLP network model

Figure 3. Schematic representations of (a) ANN model 1, (b) ANN model 2, and (c) ANN model 3 network structures

Figure 4. a) Comparison targeted air flow rate results and ANN model 1 predicted results, b) Representation of air flow experiment results and ANN model 1 results on the zero-error line, c) Deviation rates of ANN model 1 according to air flow data points

Figure 5. a) Showing the targeted air outlet temperature results and ANN model 2 predicted results, b) Representation of air outlet temperature experimental results and ANN model 2 results on the zero-error line, c) Deviation rates of ANN model 2 according to air outlet temperature data points

Figure 6. a) Comparison of targeted total cooling capacity results and ANN model 2 predicted results, b) representation of total cooling capacity experimental results and ANN model 2 results on the zero-error line, c) deviation rates of ANN model 2 according to total cooling capacity data points

Figure 7. a) Comparison of targeted coil water pressure loss results and ANN model 3 predicted results, b) illustration of water pressure loss test results and ANN model 3 results on the zero-error line, c) deviation rates of ANN model 3 according to water pressure loss data points

Figure 8. a) Comparison of targeted air outlet temperature results and ANN model 4 predicted results, b) representation of air outlet temperature experimental results and ANN model 4 results on the zero-error line, c) deviation rates of ANN model 4 according to air outlet temperature data points

Figure 9. a) Comparison of targeted total cooling capacity results and ANN model 4 predicted results, b) depiction of total cooling capacity experimental results and ANN model 4 results on the zero-error line, c) deviation rates of ANN model 4 according to total cooling capacity data points

Figure 10. a) Comparison of targeted fan power consumption results and ANN model 4 predicted results, b) representation of fan power consumption experimental results and ANN model 4 results on the zero-error line, c) deviation rates of ANN model 4 according to fan power consumption data points

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

Figure 11. SHAP analysis for ANN models (a) feature importance for ANN Model 1 predicting air flow rate, (b) feature importance for ANN Model 2 predicting air outlet temperature, (c) feature importance for ANN Model 2 predicting total cooling capacity, (d) feature importance for ANN Model 3 predicting water pressure drop, (e) feature importance for ANN Model 4 predicting air outlet temperature, (f) feature importance for ANN Model 4 predicting total cooling capacity, and (g) feature importance for ANN Model 4 predicting fan power.